

Light-Scattering Behaviour of the Acid Polysaccharides from *Lannea Grandis*

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The light-scattering behaviour of the degraded and original acid polysaccharides derived from the plant exudate, "*Lannea Grandis*", has been investigated. The Hc/T vs. c and Z vs. c plots are unique and have been explained in terms of the hard sphere model of Doty and Steiner. The variation of angular distribution of scattering with concentration for the sodium salts of the degraded and original polyacids has been studied and the results have been treated in the form of Zimm plots, wherefrom weight and number average molecular weights, and Z - and number average radii of gyration and end-to-end chain lengths have been calculated. The results of light-scattering measurements have been shown to be in good agreement with the constitution of the polysaccharide derived from chemical investigations.

The configuration of a charged macromolecule in solution is largely dependent on the extent of charge on the polyion. It is, therefore, expected that the light-scattering measurements as a function of charge may be employed for a quantitative estimation of the changes in configuration of the polyions. The light-scattering behaviour of most of the polyelectrolytes studied so far, e.g., polyvinyl pyridinium bromide¹, polymethacrylic acid²⁻⁵, sodium salt of carboxymethyl cellulose^{3,6}, sodium polyphosphate⁷, polystyrene sulphonate⁸ etc. has been found to be, more or less, in conformity with the existing theories. But the polysaccharides studied by us present a different situation. Chaudhuri⁹ studied the hydrodynamic behaviour and electrochemistry of the degraded and original acid polysaccharides isolated from the exudate of *Lannea Grandis*. He found that these systems exhibit limited coiling-uncoiling behaviour which was interpreted as being due to the inherent stiffness of the cellulosic chain.

EXPERIMENTAL

The isolation and preparation of the degraded and original acid polysaccharides and their sodium salts have been described elsewhere^{9,10}.

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1. R. M. Fuoss and D. Edelson, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1951, **6**, 767.
2. H. J. L. Trap and J. J. Hermans, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 757.
3. A. Oth and P. Doty, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, **56**, 43.
4. A. Katchalsky and H. Eisenberg, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1951 **6**, 145.
5. P. Alexander and K. A. Stacey, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1955, **57**, 291.
6. N. S. Schneider and P. J. Doty, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 762.
7. U. P. Strauss, E. H. Smith and P. L. Winemann, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 261, 6186.
8. R. A. Mock, C. A. Marshall and T. E. Slykhouse, *Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 498.
9. S. R. Chaudhuri, D. Phil. Thesis, Calcutta University, 1964.
10. A. K. Bhattacharyya and C. V. N. Rao, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1964, **42**, 107.

Light-scattering measurements were carried out with the help of a Brice-Phoenix Photometer (Model OM 1000A) based on the description of Brice *et al.*¹¹. Turbidity and dissymmetry measurements were made with a semi-octagonal cell and the angular distribution of scattering was measured with a cylindrical cell¹² having two flat faces.

The differences in refractive indices of the various solutions from those of the solvents were measured with the help of a Brice-Phoenix Differential Refractometer.

In all the experiments, green light ($\lambda = 5461 \text{ \AA}$) was employed. The solutions were slightly coloured particularly at higher concentrations, but since absorption at $5461 \text{ \AA}$ was negligible, no correction was necessary.

Dust-free water was prepared by slow distillation of conductivity water. Both the solvent and the solutions were filtered several times through sintered glass, first with G_4 and then with G_3 funnels. Dilutions of the solutions were made directly in the cells and the concentration of each of the solutions was determined by the dry weight method.

Turbidity measurements were made at different degrees of neutralisation of the degraded polyacid, e.g., at $\alpha = 0\%$, 20% , 40% and 80% , the corresponding values of the specific refractive index, dn/dc , were 0.1041 , 0.1263 , 0.1460 and 0.1000 respectively and the values of $H \times 10^6$, where H is an optical constant of Debye's turbidity equation¹³, were 1.2011 , 1.7543 , 2.3443 and 2.8154 respectively. Dissymmetry measurements of the degraded polyacid were made at $\alpha = 20\%$, 40% , and 80% . For the measurements of angular distribution of scattering, the solutions of the degraded and original polysalts were diluted isoionically with sodium chloride solution, following the procedure of Pals and Hermans¹³, using the relation $x + 1000 r c = x_0$, where $x =$ concentration of sodium chloride solution in mole/l., $r =$ number of ionized groups per gm. of polysalt, $c =$ concentration of the sodium salt of the polyacid in gm./ml., $x_0 =$ ionic strength of the solution.

The values of x_0 were 4.114×10^{-3} mole/l. and 2.892×10^{-3} mole/l. for the degraded and original polysalts respectively, these ionic strengths being due to the polysalts themselves at their highest concentrations employed. The values of dn/dc for the solutions of the degraded and original polysalts were 0.1605 and 0.1695 respectively, the corresponding values of K , an optical constant¹⁴ like H , were 0.1689×10^{-6} and 0.1885×10^{-6} respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The variation of reciprocal reduced intensity with concentration at different degrees of neutralisation of the degraded polyacid has been shown in Fig. 1. An examination of the curves reveals that the system seems to follow, at least under the experimental conditions employed, the hard sphere model as envisaged by Doty and Steiner¹⁴. At a particular degree of neutralisation, the initial slope of the Hc/T vs. c plot is considerably steep. Had the interaction of the polyions remained the same as the concentration varied, one would expect the slope to continue. It is seen, however, that along the intermediate range of concentration studied, the reciprocal reduced intensity curve levels off with increasing concen-

11. B. A. Brice, M. Halwer and R. Speiser, *J. Opt. Soc., U. S. A.* 1950, **40**, 768.
12. L. P. Witenauer and J. H. Sherr, *Rev., Sci., Instr.*, 1952, **23**, 99.
13. D. T. F. Pals and J. J. Hermans, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1952, **71**, 433, 458, 513.
14. P. Doty and R. F. Steiner, *J. Polym. Sci.* 1950, **5**, 383.

tration. This means that with increasing concentration, the slope decreases due to a diminution in the repulsive forces between the polyions and this, in turn, leads to a decrease in the value of the effective diameter of the spherical ion. At this concentration range, a larger fraction of the counterions remain bound with the polyions and consequently the charge on the latter decreases. As the concentration is further increased, the Hc/T vs. c plot rises again. This behaviour, however, cannot be easily explained. It seems that at higher

FIG. 1. Variation of reciprocal reduced turbidity with concentration of the degraded polyacid at different degrees of neutralization.

concentrations of the polyion, the excluded volume effect becomes dominant and that the higher virial coefficients come into play. Almost identical behaviour is exhibited by the polyacid at all degrees of neutralisation and the initial slope, i.e., the effective diameter increases with increasing degree of neutralisation. It is interesting to note that these results bear a close resemblance with those obtained by Veis and Eggenberger¹⁵ in the case of arabic acid.

The variation of dissymmetry with concentration at different degrees of neutralisation of the degraded polyacid is shown in Fig. 2. It is seen that with increasing concentration the dissymmetry value decreases, reaches a minimum, as expected, and then after a short upward rise almost levels off. This levelling off of the dissymmetry curve may be interpreted, as before, as due to the relatively greater increase in the value of the excluded volume. It may be noted that the dissymmetry curves at different degrees of neutralisation are almost superimposable and this is quite natural in view of the limited

FIG. 2. Variation of dissymmetry with concentration of the degraded polyacid at different degrees of neutralization.

polyelectrolyte character of these systems. Because of the uncertainty in the extrapolation of the non-linear dissymmetry plots, the intrinsic dissymmetry and hence the molecular dimensions could not be accurately determined.

For an unequivocal determination of the molecular weights and dimensions, variation of the angular distribution of scattering of the polysalts was measured as a function of concentration, and the results in the form of Zimm plots¹⁶, are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 for the degraded and original polysalts respectively. Assuming that the molecules obey

FIG. 3. Zimm plot of the degraded polysalt.

FIG. 4. Zimm plot of the original polysalt.

Gaussian and random-flight statistics for the randomly coiling chains, weight- and number-average molecular weights, $\bar{M}$, and Z- and number-average root-mean-square values of the radius of gyration, $(\bar{\rho}^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$, and end-to-end chain length, $(\bar{R}^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$, of the degraded and original polysalts were calculated from the corresponding Zimm plots. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
Molecular weights and dimensions of the polysalts

Parameters	Degraded polysalt	Original polysalt
$\bar{M}_w$	13.87×10^6	17.50×10^6
$(\bar{\rho}_w^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$	2184 Å	2242 Å
$(\bar{R}_w^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$	5350 Å	5491 Å
$\bar{M}_n$	8.21×10^5	9.80×10^5
$(\bar{\rho}_n^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$	689 Å	717 Å
$(\bar{R}_n^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$	1689 Å	1755 Å
$(\bar{M}_w/\bar{M}_n)$	16.9	17.9

The ratio of the weight average to number average molecular weights, $\bar{M}_w/\bar{M}_n$, is a measure of polydispersity. It is seen from the above table that the value of $\bar{M}_w/\bar{M}_n$ is about 17 and 18, which is indicative of an extremely wide and skewed molecular weight distribution. Such a result is expected for molecules which contain randomly placed branching points¹⁷. It may be noted that naturally occurring polymers are found to be invariably polydisperse, the ratio, $\bar{M}_w/\bar{M}_n$, amounting to very high values, e.g., for starch amylopectin a value of 287 for $\bar{M}_w/\bar{M}_n$ has been reported by Stacey and Foster¹⁸.

16. B. H. Zimm, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1948, 16, 1093, 1099.

17. S. Erlander and D. French, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1956, 26, 7.

18. C. J. Stacey and J. F. Foster, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1956, 20, 57, 1957, 25, 39.

In the polyacids under investigation, the uronic carboxyl groups are situated at random in the molecule. Therefore, after proper correction in molecular weight for the uronic carboxyl groups (from a knowledge of the equivalent weight=950), and assuming that the degraded polyacid is composed of only galactopyranose units linearly joined along the polymer chain, the number average effective bond length, b_n , was calculated with $M_0=180$, and the value was found to be 25.5 Å. Again, if we assume that the structure of the repeating unit of the degraded polyacid as assigned by Bhattacharyya *et al.* is correct, we may treat the polymer molecule, though approximately, as a linear chain composed of galactose such that two such hexose sugars (e.g., one from the linear chain and one from the side) are fused together, which form the monomer unit and consequently $M_0=2 \times 180$, but the average bond length, l , of the monomer unit remaining the same as before, i.e., 5.14 Å. Based on these assumptions, the value of the number average effective bond length, b_n , was found to be 36.1 Å. Benoit *et al.*¹¹ working with a highly polydisperse sample of cellulose nitrate of molecular weight $M_n=94,000$, found the effective bond length to be 38 Å. The close agreement between these values of the effective bond lengths suggests that the overall structure of the degraded polyacid, as suggested by Bhattacharyya *et al.* is justified.

An examination of the results presented in Table I reveals that the molecular weight of the original polysalt ($\bar{M}_w=17.5 \times 10^6$) is higher than that of the degraded sample ($\bar{M}_w=13.87 \times 10^6$). This difference in molecular weights, namely, 3.63×10^6 , must be the contribution due to the arabinose units which are absent in the degraded polysalt. Had these arabinose units been present linearly joined along the polymer backbone, then the root-mean square separation, $(\bar{R}^2_z)^{1/2}$, between the chain ends in the original polysalt must have been proportionately greater than the corresponding value of the degraded polysalt. But contrary to our expectation, the two values of $(\bar{R}^2_z)^{1/2}$ (e.g., 5491 Å and 5350 Å respectively) are found to be very close to each other. This suggests that the arabinose units are present along side-chains in the original polysaccharide. Again, the ratio of the weight of arabinose per molecule of the original polysalt, i.e., 3.63×10^6 to the weight of the latter $M_w=17.5 \times 10^6$, is found to be 4.8. The corresponding ratio, calculated on the basis of the structure of the repeating unit presented above, comes to be 4.4. The agreement between these two ratios provides an indirect evidence of the validity of the structure of the original polyacid, as proposed by Bhattacharyya *et al.*

There exists, however, considerable discrepancy regarding the molecular weights. In the present investigation the weight average molecular weight of the original polysalt has been found to be 17.5×10^6 , whereas Bhattacharyya *et al.* reported a value of 1.88×10^7 for the corresponding molecular weight of the methyl derivative of the original polyacid. It seems quite reasonable to suppose that during methylation of the polysaccharide by treatment with dimethyl sulphate and 45% sodium hydroxide solution¹¹, the polysaccharide might have undergone partial degradation and consequently decrease in molecular weight.